

ARIES

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DELIVERABLE REPORT

E-Learning course

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ABSTRACT

The aim of that activity was to setup up an e-learning course in test mode. The first year of the activity has been devoted to organising the different parts of the course. The following years have been devoted to finding coordinators and lecturers willing to contribute and then recording the course. The course is now ready in test mode, as promised for this deliverable.

ARIES Consortium, 2020

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Delivery Slip

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Executive summary

The aim of this activity consists in setting up an e-learning course in test mode. The first year of the activity has been devoted to organising the different parts of the course. The following years have been devoted to finding coordinators and lecturers willing to contribute and to record the lectures. Out of the four courses selected, two are presently available in test mode, as promised for this deliverable. The recording of additional lectures has been delayed by the current sanitary crisis but they will become soon available.

1. Introduction

A key to the development of the scientific, industrial, and societal impacts of accelerators in Europe is to have a sufficient pool of personnel trained in the topics related to particle accelerators. However, a survey conducted a few years ago identified the lack of sufficient training provision in the field in Europe (and worldwide) [1,2]. To address this need it was proposed to establish an online course aimed at training university students in fields related to particle accelerators.

The e-training course developed in this work package aims at addressing this need.

On the pedagogical side, the course will be aimed at students toward the beginning of the second cycle (master program) as defined in the European Higher Education Area (so-called Bologna process). The course duration will comprise 10 hours of online video, which is equivalent to approximately 30 hours of in-class teaching. This course will be split into 4 modules: One introductory module with an online duration of 4 hours and 3 specialization modules of 6 hours each. To complete the course students will have to complete the introductory module and one of the specialization modules.

Figure 1 shows the position of the ARIES MOOC in the European Accelerator Education landscape, as defined by ARIES WP2.

Figure 1: ARIES MOOC in the European Accelerator Education landscape

2. Course preparation

2.1 TECHNICAL AND SYLLABUS COMMITTEE

Two committees have been setup to help with the work of this task:

- A syllabus committee whose job was to identify the content of various accelerator courses across Europe and propose a syllabus for the e-learning course. The committee was also in charge of suggesting names for coordinators and course lecturers. Members of this committee were experts in the field nominated by ARIES WP2, either with teaching experience in accelerator courses in Europe or as experts in pedagogy.
- A technical committee that focussed on technical issues such as deciding how to organize the course and which licensing scheme to use. Members of this committee were experts in digital technologies or online courses.

The membership of these committees is given in Annex 2.

2.2 OUTCOME OF THE COURSE PREPARATION

The work of the two committee has been summarized in a paper presented during the International Particle Accelerator Conference IPAC'18 [3] and available at:

<https://espace.cern.ch/project-ARIESIntranet/WP2/Shared%20Documents/WG2.4/MOPML050.pdf>

This paper outlines the content of the full course (not only the test part) and how the recording will be organized. The syllabus was decided by the committee based on what expert felt is the most important for second cycle students to learn. Important input were received from the Accelerators schools on what they would like student to have learnt before coming. The detailed syllabus is given in the next section. It was decided that the course would be divided in two modules, an introductory module and an advanced module.

2.3 SYLLABUS

The course syllabus has been defined as follows:

- **Introductory module: Introduction to accelerators (4 hours)**
An introductory course about accelerators.
 - What is an accelerator?
 - Applications of accelerators and the future.
 - Electromagnetism with no pre-requisites.
 - Relativity with no pre-requisites.
- **Advanced module:**
- **Accelerator Physics (6 hours)**

Aimed at physics students who would like to understand what particle accelerators are, how they work, what happens inside the accelerators and what limits the performance of modern accelerators. The focus here is on physical processes.

- Maxwell equations and application to the propagation of electromagnetic waves at radio frequencies.
 - Statistical physics applied to an electron gas; collective effects.
 - Colliders (accelerators for High Energy Physics; accelerators for Nuclear Physics), neutrons facilities and synchrotron radiation facilities.
 - Medical applications and other applications.
 - Future European and international facilities and their applications.
 - The future: higher gradient, higher intensities, higher reliability, laser-plasma acceleration, ...
- Accelerator Engineering (6 hours)

Aimed at engineering students who would like to understand what particle accelerators are, how they work, what happens inside the accelerators and what limits the performances of modern accelerators. The focus here is on the engineering aspects of accelerators.

- Maxwell equations and application to the propagation of electromagnetic waves at radio frequencies.
 - Diagnostics, uncertainty in measurements, propagation of charged particles through matter and radiation emitted by particles.
 - Advanced topics in radio-frequency and high voltages.
 - Magnet design and cryogenics.
 - Vacuum technology and mechanical engineering for accelerators.
 - Radioprotection and safety at particle accelerators.
 - The future: higher gradient, higher intensities, higher reliability, laser-plasma acceleration, ...
- Applications of accelerators (6 hours)
- For students who would like to learn what accelerators are, how there are used and how they impact our society.
- Colliders (accelerators for High Energy Physics; accelerators for Nuclear Physics), neutrons facilities and synchrotron radiation facilities.
 - Diagnostics, uncertainty in measurements, propagation of charged particles through matter and radiation emitted by particles.
 - Medical, industrial and other applications.
 - Synchrotron radiation physics.
 - Overview and operation of medical accelerators and other small facilities.
 - Radiation protection and safety at particle accelerators.
 - Machine detectors interface at colliders, synchrotron light sources and neutron sources.
 - Future European and international facilities and their applications.

3. Course realization

Following the recommendation of the syllabus committee several persons were approached to coordinate part of the training and 4 were selected. They were in charge of finding 2-3 lecturers to work with them on the preparation of their course, respecting a good balance between gender, age and country of origin.

After the appointment of the course coordinators there were regular meetings either by teleconference or in person to discuss the programme and check that the detailed content of the course was suitable to the target audience.

By the end the summer 2019 two of the courses were advanced enough to schedule their recording. This recording took place at the CERN Media Centre in December 2019 and continued in January 2020.

The editing of these courses took place in February and a final review meeting for the Relativity course was scheduled for March 17th in Orsay.

Due to the ban on travels to France, this meeting was re-organised as a remote meeting using online editing tools and then the compulsory lockdown imposed in France on March 15th converted this meeting to long exchanges of emails with comments on the video.

The team is now working remotely to finalize the editing of these videos.

The **Relativity** course is **available in test mode** at:

http://particle-accelerators.eu/?page_id=81

(while the videos are still being edited, they are protected by the password “Einstein” but this should disappear shortly).

The **Electromagnetism** course is **available in test mode** at:

http://particle-accelerators.eu/?page_id=87

(while the videos are still being edited, they are protected by the password “Maxwell” but this should disappear shortly).

The recording of the **Application** course will take place as soon as the compulsory containment will be lifted in Europe (as lecturers come from several countries: France, Spain, Switzerland, Poland and UK, the recording will be dependent on the traveling conditions for the different European countries). The recording of the **Introduction to Accelerators** course should follow soon after.

Once these recordings are completed and edited the full introductory module will be available at: http://particle-accelerators.eu/?page_id=24 .

4. Future plans / Conclusion / relation to other ARIES work

Beyond the introductory module, work on some courses of the advanced module has started and will continue until the end of the ARIES project.

Several University lecturers have volunteered to ask their students to take this online course and give us feedback. This feedback will be useful in adjusting the future modules.

We expect to be able to switch this online course from test mode to production mode before September 2021.

Beyond this project, we hope that this course will be useful to the accelerator community and we are considering different options to make it sustainable, updating it and adding new courses as needed.

5. References

[1] F. Kircher et al. Education and Training Survey Report: Deliverable 5.1. Tech. rep. TIARA-REP-WP5-2012-006. Geneva: CERN, Apr. 2012. <https://cds.cern.ch/record/1442599>

[2] P. Burrows et al. Recommendations for promoting accelerator science and technology in Europe: Deliverable 5.4. Tech. rep. TIARA-REP-WP5-2013-016. Geneva: CERN, Nov. 2013. <https://cds.cern.ch/record/1627600>

[3] N. Delerue et al., A Massive Open Online Course on Particle Accelerators, J.Phys.Conf.Ser. 1067 (2018) 9, 092004

Annex 1: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
MOOC	Massive Online Open Course

Annex:2: Membership of the committes

An approximative membership of the two committees is given here:

Syllabus committee:

Phil Burrows (University of Oxford)

Graeme Burt (University of Lancaster)

Eric Briantais (Université Paris-Sud)

Erik Bründermann (KIT)

Marica Biagini (INFN)

Alessandro Cianchi (Università degli Studi di Roma "Tor Vergata")

Jennifer Toes (CERN)

Christine Darve (ESS)

Soren Pape Moller (ISA, Aarhus)

Eleonore Douarche (Université Paris-Sud)

Romuald Drot (Université Paris-Sud)

Fredrik Hellberg (Univserity of Stockholm)

Philippe Lebrun (JUAS)

Louis Rinolfi (JUAS)

Sergey Polozov (Moscow University)

Hermann Schmickler (CAS)

Ansgar Simonsson (University of Stockholm)

Toms Torims ([Riga](#) Technical University)

Rutambhara Yogi (ESS)

Nicolas Delerue (CNRS)

Technical committee:

Phil Burrows (University of Oxford)

Eric Briantais (Université Paris-Sud)

Gabriel Mathevet (Université Paris-Sud)

Julius Kvissberg ([Eduvid company](#))

Sergey Polozov ([University](#) of Moscow)

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